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Executive summary

The following document describes the implementation and functioning of the Heliospectra lighting system in the EDEN ISS project. The overview is based on collected data and measurements before and during the Antarctic deployment phase. The following document describes the functioning, stability and maintenance of the Lighting System (LS) and contains, among others, light output and thermal stability information based on collected data. It also contains guidelines for future improvements to the functionality of the system and the possibility to further increase the energy efficiency of plant production.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
CPU	Central processing unit	PAR	Photosynthetically active radiation
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	PC	Power consumption
LS	Lighting System	TCS	Temperature Control System
ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack	UI	User interface
MTF	Mobile Test Facility		

1 Lighting System design evaluation

1.1 Lighting System design overview

A total of 44 WX (water-cooled) Heliospectra fixtures were used during the operation phase of the EDEN ISS project. 42 WX were used within the FEG and 2 WX within the ISPR. One WX was mounted over each tray in the short and tall compartments (see Figure 1-1). Each WX installed over the short trays had a maximal power of 120W. Fixtures installed over the tall trays had maximal power of 240W. Fixtures were not used at full power capacity.

No design changes in design, placement or functionality of top fixtures were made in relation to the original Lighting System Design Document. Light settings and consequently used light intensity could deviate from the original plan. Also, the use of lightbars was limited to only one production cycle.

Figure 1-1: FEG rack and tray configuration.

1.2 Lighting System functionality

The lighting system proved to be robust and relatively problem free. The goal of providing light suitable for healthy plant production was achieved. The dynamic light schedule allowed for adjustment of the light intensity and quality to the needs of variety of crop plants and allowed light colour adjustment for both visual and automatic plant monitoring.

Figure 1-2: Top light fixtures operating over shelves in FEG. Photo by P. Zabel, 21.03.2018

2 Lighting System Performance

2.1 Light output and power usage

The light capacity of the fixtures was higher than required for optimal crop growth, as shown during the demonstration phase. During the Antarctic deployment phase, the light output was monitored with a hand-held Li-cor light meter and during the plants development it was adjusted to the crop requirements and height, when needed, according to the protocol and specifications in the Cultivation Recipes. Consequently, the typical average fixture power use rarely exceeded 64% of input power capacity, and only fixtures used for tall (vine) crops were used at full power.

Figures 2-1 a-g illustrate the midday (maximal during the photoperiod) setting for the blue LED channel for the separate fixtures used during the deployment phase. Note that due to unbalanced settings and differing energy consumption of different LED channels (see also Table 2-1) the settings for Blue LED correspond to:

- setting 60% - circa 51.5% of the total electric capacity of 240W fixture;
- setting 90% - 63% and 69% total capacity for 120W and 240W units, respectively;
- setting 100% - 92% and 100% total capacity for 120W and 240W units, respectively.

Figure 2-1 a-g: Usage of blue LED channel (maximal settings for a day, % of power capacity) during the experiment.

Table 2-1: Overview of nominal electrical power consumption (PC) and plate temperature of fixtures.

Luminaire position	Luminaire PC			Settings B, R, FR, W (% current)	Average nominal PC ² ±5%			Plate temp. ³ [°C]	
	nominal [W]	measured [W] ±2.5%	capacity usage ¹		midday [W]	daily [kW]	Per h [Wh]	1 st unit	2 ^{ed} – 1 st
L2-1 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.94	35.5	24.6	0.9
L2-2 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.94	35.5	25	0.1
L2-3 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.94	35.5	25	1.3
L2-4 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.94	35.5	24.5	0.5
L3-1 L&R	120	114	83.50%	100,72,100,90	100.2	1.6	63.1	25.7	0.6
L3-2 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.83	31.2	25.1	0.2
L3-2 L	120	114	37.70%	68,27,100,33	45.27	-	-	-	-
L3-3 L&R	120	114	83.50%	100,72,100,90	100.2	1.6	63.1	26	1.2
L3-4 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.94	35.5	24.1	1.2
L4-1 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.94	35.5	24.6	1.4
L4-2 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.94	35.5	24.5	1.2
L4-3 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.94	35.5	24.7	0.5
L4-4 L&R	120	114	48.10%	90,36,100,44	57.7	0.94	35.5	24.8	0.4
L1-2 L&R	240	252	51.5%	60,17,100,20	130	2.15	89.4	28.2	2.3
L1-4 L&R	240	252	51.5%	60,17,100,20	130	2.15	89.4	26.3	3.3
R1-2 L&R	240	252	51.5%	60,17,100,20	130	2.15	89.4	27	0.7
R1-4 L&R	240	252	51.5%	60,17,100,20	130	2.15	89.4	25.5	1.3
R2-2 L&R	240	252	51.5%	60,17,100,20	130	2.15	89.4	25.3	1
R2-4 L&R	240	252	51.5%	60,17,100,20	130	2.15	89.4	25.5	2.1
R4-2 L&R	240	252	68.7%	90,36,100,44	173.1	2.8	117.6	26.7	3
R4-4 L&R	240	252	27.2%	5,3,50,6	68.4	1.1	47.6	24.17	0.8
R3-2 L&R	240	252	100%	100,100,100,100	252	4.45	185.5	30.2	0.1

¹⁾ Typical wall plug electrical power consumption measured during end of line test, can vary by up to 5% due to LED and other electric components individual characteristics.

²⁾ Average PC is calculated for the period between 14.08 and 12.09 based on end of line test data and can vary due to individual fixture variation and temperature differences.

³⁾ Example of instantaneous temperature obtained from a fixture diagnostic file.

2.2 Thermal performance

The operating (LED plate) temperatures were maintained in the range between 20 and 35 °C ensuring the LED output efficiency and stability (por. **Error! Reference source not found.** in LS Design Document). Figure 2-2 illustrates the LED plate temperature variation for one of the fixtures during the deployment phase of the project. The atypical variation in temperature was caused by problems with TCS and leakages of the coolant.

Fixtures were connected in series of two to the cooling system. The LED temperature of the second fixture was higher by 0.1 – 3.3 °C (Table 2-1) but did not exceed optimal temperatures.

Figure 2-2: Example of LED plate temperature variation.

2.3 Power consumption

Growing plants in a closed environment requires high energy input. The total energy consumption by the lighting system during the Antarctica mission (18.02 – 23.11.2018) was 19.6 MWh (for details see table 2.2). Measured PC was lower than calculated PC, particularly for 120W fixtures. It can be an effect of small differences between conditions during testing and actual operating conditions, as well as higher electric efficiency of hardware when operating at lower current as designed.

Table 2-2: Overview of measured electrical power consumption [kWh] for lighting total and examples for a pair of luminaires. Luminaries L1-2 (2 fixtures) – 240 W lamps with varying schedule settings, R1-4 – 240W luminaire with 51.5% max settings, L2-1 -120W luminaires with 48% max settings.

Period	LS right	LS left	total	LED L1-2	LED R1-4	LED L2-1
Feb-18	988	1084	2072	79	75	38
Mar-18	1106	974	2080	153	109	54
Apr-18	1049	1003	2052	175	108	54
May-18	1092	945	2037	125	111	56
Jun-18	1038	800	1838	97	103	50
Jul-18	1108	1077	2185	179	110	55
Aug-18	1002	982	1984	126	111	55
Sep-18	945	954	1899	120	107	57
Oct-18	996	963	1959	165	105	53
Nov-18	756	743	1499	131	78	39
Total	10080	9525	19605	1350	1017	511

2.4 Lightbars (side lighting)

The lightbars installed in unit R3 were used only for the first cucumber cultivation cycle. After recognizing that the leaves were burnt by the lights, as the back row of shoots were basically touching the bars, they were turned off for the second cycle.

2.5 Communication

The lamps were controlled through ARGUS system. No problems with communication with lamps occurred.

2.6 Aging of optical components

The conditions of the FEG and the instruments taken for the mission do not allow for any in-situ precision measurements needed for the assessments of LEDs and optical components. The light measurements with a Li-cor PAR meter conducted after the experiment was inconclusive. However, we can expect lower fixture efficiency decline than predicted due to lower than usual operating temperatures.

The proper measurements of the fixtures' light output reduction can be done only in an optical laboratory and the lamps will not be brought back to Europe before the publishing of this report.

2.7 Light settings and light intensity

Light settings during the experiments can be found from Figures 2-1 a-g and Table 2-1.

The accurate assessment of the lighting conditions that the crops were exposed to during the experiment is very difficult. Table 2-3 illustrates the problem. Due to the high reflectivity of the FEG, the light settings measured without plants are typically higher, due to larger contribution (reflection) from the other lamps (light measurements "after" experiment) than from the plants. Light setpoints were determined (in measurements "before" the experiment) with the FEG partially populated by growing crops. Additionally, the light situation was changing dynamically during the growth of the plants, due to growth and harvest on the neighbouring trays. Overall light intensity was higher than planned.

Table 2-3: Overview of the light intensity in FEG. The higher values "after" are explained by a high contribution from other lamps after removing plants.

Unit (lamp)	Settings in %	PAR ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)					
		at 16 cm		at 25 cm		at 60 cm	
		before	after	before	after	before	after
L1-2R	90,36,100,44	-	348	450	398	-	1245
	60,17,100,20	-	248	305	290	-	930
	18,15,60,15	-	200	-	240	652	740
L2-1L	90,36,100,44	330	378	660	750	-	-
	68,27,100,33	235	290	500	550	-	-
Unit (lamp)	Settings in %	At 30 cm				At 60 cm	
R3-4R	100,100,100,100	-	-	170	170	210	270

Before – measurements conducted during light settings, before exploration phase on 30.06.2017

After – measurements conducted after finishing the experiment in Antarctica on 30.11.2018

Photoperiod consisted of 15h of “day” light and 1h of “sunrise” and 1h of “sunset”

Sunrise and sunset consisted of 15 minutes of low white light with approximately the same amount of FR as PAR-enriched light with the R:FR ratio of 0.3. The intensity depends on distance but for 120 W lamps was c. 24 micromoles PAR at 15 cm. The FR rich light was followed (at sunrise) or preceded (at sunset) with 45 minutes of half settings, so more or less half the light intensity.

Figure 2-3: Light composition during the photoperiod.

2.8 Plant health and growth performance

The goal of healthy plant production was achieved with high plant production. A total of 77 kilograms of lettuce, 51 kilograms of cucumber, 29 kilograms of tomato, 12 kilograms of kohlrabi, 5 kilograms of radish and 9 kilograms of herbs have been grown and harvested

However, it is difficult to draw a conclusion regarding efficiency since there is no reference point. The growth performance depends on all environmental factors, including the harvesting method, and not on the lighting system alone. Therefore, the analysis of crop productivity is outside of the scope of this document and will be done in a separate publication.

Figure 2-4: Plant growth and harvesting in the FEG

3 System Maintenance and Observed Issues

The protocol did not require any maintenance procedures of the Lighting System, other than occasional light intensity adjustments based on individual crop requirements and periodic lamp cover cleaning. These procedures were carried out as planned.

An (until now) undiagnosed failure occurred with one of the LED lamps at the end of April (Table 3-1). A spare lamp was installed. The fixture will be checked on its return. The failure was preceded by a major Thermal Control System failure and temporary shutdown of the Lighting System, which may suggest that events were connected.

Table 3-1: List of issues which had a direct impact on LS functioning and continuous provision of light for the crops

Date	Description	Cause	Action taken
13.03	ISPR unit failure		'Burning' smell from the left atmosphere management system of ISPR GCS or ISPR NDS drawer. ISPR switched off completely.
18.04	Some LED lamps shutting off periodically due to TCS issues.	TCS control failure	
27.04	unit L2-3R failure	Problem not diagnosed on side.	Spare unit installed. The lamp sent back for diagnostics via Polarstern boat, will not reach Europe before publication of this document.
18.05	Lamps shutting off because of overheating	Low pressure in external cooling loop	External cooling loop repressurized to 1.2 bar.
19.06	Leak in L1-4. Lamps in L1 shut down.		ILS/ISPR cooling loop pressurized to 1.2 bar. Leak glued.
29.06	LED lamps turned off	Plate heat exchanger in LED/ISPR and AMS cooling loop frozen due to very low temperatures of -20 °C in the external cooling loop, the cooling fluid on the secondary side of the plate exchangers froze and blocked circulation in the cooling loops.	Cooling fluid of AMS and LED/ISPR cooling loop exchanged with fluid with lower freezing temperature.

Proper functioning of water-cooled fixtures depends on faultless operation of the Thermal Control System (TCS), which proved to be vulnerable to low external temperatures, and suffered from leakages. Table 3-2 provides a list of TCS issues, which were not related directly to the LS, but had an impact on lighting stability and the thermal performance of the light fixtures.

Table 3-2: List of thermal system issues

Date	Description	S/S	Actions taken	Cause
07.08	Leak in external cooling loop Screw connection on WT1 pump outflow got loose.	TCS	Insulation removed from cooling pipes to search for leak spot. Screw connection loosened, dried and tightened again. External cooling loop pressurized to 1.5 bar.	Attempt to increase pressure in external cooling loop to 1.5 bar. Screw connection got loose, and several liters of cooling fluid was spilled.
19.07	Freezing of freecooler 3-way valve actuator again	TCS	See ID 19.06	See 19.06
29.06	Plate heat exchanger in LED/ISPR and AMS cooling loop frozen	TCS	Cooling fluid of AMS and LED/ISPR cooling loop exchanged with fluid with lower freezing temperature.	Due to very low temperatures of -20 °C in the external cooling loop, the cooling fluid on the secondary side of the plate exchangers froze and blocked circulation in the cooling loops.
29.06	Freezing of freecooler 3-way valve actuator again	TCS	Actuator removed for inspection and drying. ILS turned off for the night.	See 19.06
21.06	Pressure drop in external cooling loop 0.6 bar	TCS	None.	Unknown.
19.06	Freezing of freecooler 3-way valve actuator Overheating of cooling loops, due to freecooler 3-way valve being stuck in close position.	TCS	Actuator removed for inspection and drying. ILS turned off for the night.	Freecooler fan turned on manually. This caused a temperature drop in the external cooling loop to -15 °C.
19.06	Low pressure in LED/ISPR cooling loop	TCS	Leak in L1-4. Lamps in L1 shut down. ILS/ISPR cooling loop pressurized to 1.2 bar. Leak glued.	Leak found in L1-4.
07.06	Low pressure in LED/ISPR cooling loop	TCS	Probably leak.	No leak could be found.
18.05	Low pressure in external cooling loop	TCS	External cooling loop repressurized to 1.2 bar.	
18.05	One freecooler fan broken	TCS	Broken fan disconnected from freecooler control box so that the remaining fan can work.	
16.05	Pressure drop in external cooling loop	TCS	None.	Probably shrinking of cooling fluid, due to very low external temperatures.
09.05	Freecooler fuse went off	TCS	Fuse needs to be replaced with	Unknown.

			stronger one.	
07.05	Pressure deviation in external cooling loop 0.8-1.1 bar depending on vlave position	TCS	None.	Unknown.
07.05	Freecooler fuse went off	TCS	Fuse needs to be replaced with stronger one.	Unknown.
18.04	TCS control failure CDH did not maintain proper control of the TCS valves. Temperature in FEG around 28 °C, relative humidity >85 %.	CDH	CDH reset to state of 16.04.	Event caused by new set points in the PID control of the TCS valves. New set points were set in order to try to lower the humidity inside the FEG.
12.04	New ISPR THC-L unit is leaking cooling fluid.	ISPR	Connections checked and sealed.	No Teflon tape on thread of tube adapter.
08.04	Pressure in external cooling loop dropped to 0.9 bar. Periodically dropped to 0.8 bar causing audible alarm.	TCS	Cooling fluid added and repressurized to 1.3 bar.	Very cold temperatures (< -35°C). Probably cooling fluid shrank due to the very low temperatures. No leak could be detected.
12.03	Leak in WT2 cooling loop See 24.02. Failure was discovered relatively early, around one hour later. Less cooling fluid leaked than before.	TCS	O-rings were replaced by new rubber O-rings. Large cable ties have been added to relief some of the tension on the connection.	Cause unknown. Probably screw connection was tightened too much and O-ring shifted its position. Low temperatures of the cooling fluid might lead to shrinking of the metal tube and screw connection causing a leak. Humidifier needs to be turned off, as long as TCS is offline for repair.
24.02	Leak in WT2 cooling loop Cooling fluid was leaking from the screw connection at the outlet of pump WT2. Almost all fluid of the external cooling loop emptied into the service section basin. Pressure in the line went to 0 bar. Temperatures in the other cooling loops were rising.	TCS	Screw connection as opened and the seals and flow-back valve inspected. No visible signs of damage of the seals. Sealing O-rings were cleaned, Vaseline was put on and the O-rings were put back into the screw connection. Fluid was pumped back into the cooling loop and the leak appeared to be sealed.	Cause unknown. Screw connection might have gotten lose during the transport of the MTF. O-ring seals might have moved during transport of the MTF.

4 On-Site System Improvements

No improvements were implemented on site.

5 Lessons Learned and Proposed Future System Improvements

5.1 Capacity of the Lighting System

The LS was designed to fit the shelf system of FEG. As planned, the capacity of the system was not used to its full extent. This was partly because the system specifications had to be fixed before the experiments optimising the light quality (spectra) for plant production were carried out. The gathered knowledge and experience may allow better assessment of system capacity needed in the future.

The reduction of system capacity by as much as 36% is possible and should still allow for sufficient flexibility in light control. In low light units (e.g. germination area) the application of lighter luminaires (e.g. lightbars with dimming function) may be recommended.

The lightbars used at the sides (side or inter-canopy lighting) are not practical in limited space. The contribution of light from other units is sufficient to provide healthy light conditions for vine crops.

5.2 Light quality and intensity

Maintaining stable light conditions for quick growing crops was not executed as needed. The excessively elevated light intensity might have increased stress symptoms visible in tall crops, such as pepper and tomato (though the primary stress might have been caused by a nutrient imbalance). The problem can be attenuated or excluded by incorporating light sensors and automatic light intensity adjustment in a future plant growth facility. Such a control system already exists and is commercially available (e.g. helioCORE by Heliospectra), however its usability in an indoor environment has been questioned. Light sensors may be used to adjust and stabilize the light environment, and to account for the contribution of light from neighbouring units. Implementing additional sensors to monitor progress in plant growth (distance of plant canopy to lamps) may also be recommended. Such a system, automatically adjusting light intensity to growing crops (keeping them in optimal light condition) lowers the amount of human labour required and limits energy consumption during plant growth. It may also increase the predictability of harvest and allow some control over speed of crop production.

The choice of dynamic light settings (with sunset and sunrise) is beneficial for crop growth performance. It allows the photoperiod to be extended with a lower energy consumption when comparing to static light. Therefore, a dynamic lighting system can be recommended for both space plant growing and terrestrial applications, such as indoor farming and plant factories.

5.3 Water-cooled lighting system

The water-cooled lighting system has advantages and disadvantages. Among the advantages, the most important is the excellent level of thermal control for both the LED plate and the plant growth conditions (temperature in FEG). Maintaining the operating temperature of the LED plate at 25°C assures maximal quantum efficiency of electric conversion and extends the life of the luminaire. Also, the plants are not damaged when they touch luminaire.

However, lamp operation depends on faultless functioning of the cooling and heat exchange system and may be affected by leakage. The multiple problems observed during the mission were specific to the EDEN ISS system. The company who built the thermal control system and installed the components had not considered the specific requirements of the Antarctic environment. Also, some manu-

facturing errors were made in the choice of materials with different thermal expansion properties, resulting in occasional leakages. Water-cooling systems require more careful design and explanation.

Due to similar problems occurring in other (test and commercial) installations the water-cooled system was withdrawn from the market.

It is also heavy, which is a major obstacle in a space application. Re-designing or using an alternative cooling method (e.g. air cooling) should be considered.

References

N/A.